

BLOOD TRANSFUSION NEEDS IN ORTHOPEDIC CARE: INSIGHTS FROM RIVERS STATE UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL

Amina Grace Ekechi

Department of Hematology and Blood Transfusion, Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20140573>

A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>Background: Blood transfusion holds a significant place in the practice of surgery, including orthopaedic surgeries. The aim of this study was to evaluate the intraoperative use of blood and blood products among orthopaedic patients operated at the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital from January 2021 to December 2021, focusing on the demographics of patients, number and type of surgeries needing a blood transfusion, and the number of blood transfusions.</p> <p>Methodology: A retrospective observational study was carried out at the operating theatre of a referral tertiary hospital using a designed proforma to extract data from the registers of operated orthopaedic patients.</p> <p>Results: There were 168 males and 145 females who were operated on, and 43 (13.74%) of them had intraoperative blood transfusion. Patients between 41 to 50 years and 51 to 60 years dominated the distribution with a total of 20 (46.5%), out of 59 blood transfusions carried out. The surgical condition requiring the highest number of blood transfusions was fractures (29), followed by foot gangrene (17) occasioned by diabetes mellitus and peripheral vascular disease. Open reduction and internal fixation for fractures (18) constituted the highest single type of surgery carried out within the study period.</p> <p>Conclusion: A bimodal age distribution was observed in intraoperative blood transfusion requirements. The orthopaedic intraoperative blood transfusion burden was 13.74%, mainly for open reduction and internal fixation for fractures.</p>	<p>Blood Transfusion; Orthopedic Patients; Theatre; RSUTH; Port Harcourt; Nigeria.</p>

Introduction

Blood transfusion holds a significant place in the practice of surgery, including orthopedic surgeries.^[1, 2] In orthopedic practice, tumor surgeries, pelvic surgeries, and arthroplasties are often associated with heavy blood loss, although efforts are made to conserve blood loss.^[3-6] Recommendations for the implementation of a patient blood management program were based on three laudable pillars of optimizing patient's erythropoiesis, minimizing blood loss, and optimizing tolerance of anemia.^[7, 8] The modern trend in the use of blood is that of limiting the indications as much as possible to specific blood components needed by the patient. However, whole (fresh) blood transfusion may be indicated in some extreme and austere circumstances, and also when

conventional component therapy is unavailable.^[9] This same vital circulating fluid that carries oxygen and nutrients to the cells of the body for usage and delivers carbon dioxide and other waste products of metabolism for excretion from the body, is held sacred by some,^[10-12] and prohibited for transfusion by some,^[13, 14] yet life-saving and still in use.^[15,17] This calls for sensitivity of practitioners in its use, and adherence to best practices when usage is indicated. The use of specific blood components is the recommended best approach; however, blood component separation machines / equipment is not available in most service centers. Additionally, although the use of blood - whole blood, packed cells, red blood cells, etc. - has been categorized by the World Health Organization as part of essential drugs,^[18, 19] availability of these blood products has been limited by nonavailability of blood component separation machine/equipment, thereby affecting compliance. There are global challenges of insufficiency of blood and its products, among others, across the globe, especially in low and middle-income countries.^[20, 21] Recently, the issue of blood deserts has become topical,^[22] where the clinical need for blood transfusion in certain geographical areas are unmet in at least 75% in a timely and affordable manner. The need for innovations and the use of certain strategies have therefore been reported including the use of walking blood banks, intraoperative blood transfusion, and drone-based blood delivery.^[22] Challenges are boundless, as could be seen in a recent report from Colombia in South America which suggested that there was improper prescription of the use of red blood cell transfusion.^[23] In Africa and Nigeria in particular, the challenges are enormous. Whole blood/fresh whole blood was reported as the most commonly transfused among children receiving chemotherapy in a tertiary hospital in Uyo, Nigeria.^[24] A report across Nigeria also that 78% of hospitals were unable to regularly transfuse blood due to scarcity, as 45% were able to provide packed red blood cells, and only one center was able to provide leukocyte-depleted blood.^[25] We do not have a facility for component separation at our center, and we do not also have information on the burden of blood transfusion among orthopedic cases in our area of practice hence the study. Additionally, there are no previously published data on blood transfusion indices among orthopedic patients. The aim of this study was to evaluate the intraoperative use of blood and blood products blood among orthopedic surgical patients operated at the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital from January 2020 to December 2021, focusing on the demographics of patients, number and type of surgeries needing blood transfusion and the number of blood transfusions.

Methodology

Research Design: A retrospective observational study was carried out.

Study Area: The study was conducted in Port Harcourt, the capital city of Rivers State, and Nigeria.

Study Sites: The orthopedic theatre of the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital was used for the study.

Study Population: All patients who underwent emergency and elective orthopedic surgical procedures at the orthopedic theatre of the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital formed the study population.

Study Instrument: A proforma was developed for this study to capture data from the operating theatre register on blood transfusion for emergency and elective orthopaedic cases.

Variables of Interest: Patients' demographics, total number of operated patients, total number of patients transfused, indications for surgeries involving blood transfusions, type of surgery done.

Blood Transfusion Indices: Crossmatch to transfusion ratio (C: T ratio) refers to the number of units cross-matched divided by the number of units transfused. A value of < 2.5 is considered efficient blood use.^[26] Transfusion Index (TI) refers to the number of units transfused divided by the number of patients cross-matched. A TI value of >0.5 is indicative of significant blood utilization. Transfusion Probability (TP %) is the number of

patients transfused divided by the number of patients cross-matched, and the value multiplied by 100. When the value is $\geq 30\%$ it is considered as significant blood usage. [26]

Data Analysis: Data was entered in an Excel spreadsheet and exported to SPSS version 23.0 for analysis. Data was expressed as percentages of mean \pm standard deviation.

Results

Table 1 shows the sex distribution of operated patients and those who had an intraoperative blood transfusion within the study period. A total of 313 orthopaedic patients were operated on, and 43 (13.74%) of them had an intraoperative blood transfusion. There were 168 males and 145 females. Patients within 41 to 50, and 51 to 60 years dominated the distribution with a total of 20 (46.5%), and patients within 71-80 years were 9 in total amounting to 20.9%.

Table 1: Socio-demographics of patients and frequency of blood transfusion

Sex distribution for all study subjects		
Male		168
Female		145
Total		313
Sex distribution and frequency for subjects who had blood transfusion		
Male		18 (5.75%)
Female		25 (7.98%)
Total		43 (13.74%)
Age distribution of study subjects		
S/N	Age Range (Years)	Number
1	<1	0
2	1 - 10	2
3	11 - 20	3
4	21 - 30	1
5	31 - 40	2
6	41 - 50	12
7	51 - 60	8
8	61 -70	2
9	71 - 80	9
10	81 - 90	3
11	> 90	1
Mean Age (54.1Years)		

Table 2 shows orthopaedic surgical conditions and number of pints of blood transfusions Per Case. A total of 59 blood transfusions were carried out for 43 orthopaedic cases. The surgical condition requiring the highest number of blood transfusion was fractures (29), followed by foot gangrene (17) occasioned by diabetes mellitus and peripheral vascular disease. Foot gangrene also accounted for the second prevalent operated surgical condition

needing blood transfusion. The total number of units of blood transfused was 59, and the total number of patients transfused was 43, giving a Transfusion Index of 1.37.

Table 2: Surgical Conditions and Number of Pints of Blood Transfusions per Case (n = 43)

S/N	Orthopedic Conditions	Number of Pints Transfused Per Case										Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Congenital												
1	Polydactyly	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Trauma												
2	Humeral Fracture	1	3	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	6
3	Pelvic / Iliac Bone Fracture	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
4	Femoral Neck Fracture	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	-	-	-	8
5	Inter-trochanteric Fracture	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
6	Femoral Shaft Fracture	2	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	7
7	Tibia / Fibula Fracture	1	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
Metabolic												
8	Severe Hip Arthritis	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
9	Gangrene (Diabetic / Peripheral vascular Disease)	1	1	2	2	2	2	4	1	1	1	17
Infective												
11	Cellulitis / Foot Ulcer	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	8
12	Chronic Osteomyelitis	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Neoplastic												
13	Synovial Sarcoma	2										2
Total number of Pints of Blood Transfused												59

The type of surgery done and intra-operatively blood transfusions given is shown in Table 3. Open reduction and internal fixation for fractures (18) constituted the highest single type of surgery carried out within the study period. This is closely followed by below knee amputation and hemi-arthroplasty.

Table 3: Type of Surgery and Intra-operatively Blood Transfusions Given (n = 43)

S/N	Surgery	Number of Cases	Number of Pints of Blood Transfused
1	Wound Debridement	4	5
2	Skin Grafting	1	1
3	Excision Biopsy	1	1

4	External Fixation	1	1
5	Plate Removal for Previous Open Reduction and Internal Fixation (ORIF)	1	2
6	Removal of Extra Digit	1	1
7	Hemi-arthroplasty	7	10
8	ORIF for Humeral Fracture	2	4
9	ORIF for Humeral and Tibial Fractures	1	2
10	ORIF for Inter-trochanteric Fracture (Femur)	1	2
11	ORIF for Femoral Shaft Fractures	7	8
12	ORIF for Tibial and Fibula Fractures	2	2
13	Above Knee Amputation	5	7
14	Below Knee Amputation	9	13
Total		43	59

Discussion

The use of blood and blood products in surgical practice is almost like inseparable twins even in the best centers, hence its safety and availability are critical issues to the World Health Organization.^[27] This study focused on the total number of orthopedic patients transfused, indications for surgeries involving blood transfusions, and the type of surgeries done. Only whole blood and sedimented cells were transfused in this study, and out of 313 orthopaedic patients operated on, 43 (13.74%) of them had an intra-operative blood transfusion, and the male: female ratio was 1.4:1. The implication of this finding is that blood transfusion is needed in approximately 14% of orthopaedic surgeries for which males relatively dominated for both emergency and elective surgeries. This information could be a useful guide to the blood bank in making preparation for orthopaedic surgical practice in our environment. A multicentre study carried out in four Canadian hospitals revealed the use of red blood cells among 10.3% of operated orthopaedic patients, however, there was variation in rate depending on the type of surgery considered.^[28] Our study differs from the Canadian study in that red blood cells were used in that study. In this study, it was predominantly used of allogeneic whole blood and sedimented cells. Patients between the ages of 41 to 50, and 51 to 60 years were more involved in orthopaedic intraoperative blood transfusion, amounting to 46.5% of the total number. This was closely followed by patients in their seventies. The likely explanation for this observation could be that patients in this age range are those who in society were the active population engaged in several occupations involving going out to work to care for their families. This reasoning is further strengthened by the fact that trauma / open reduction and internal fixation were the most prevalent conditions/surgeries requiring intraoperative blood transfusion in our setting. Patients in their seventies were more likely to have metabolic orthopaedic conditions - diabetes mellitus and peripheral vascular disease/hypertension that account for cases of foot gangrene requiring amputations. The dominance of males in the demographics of

this study is similar to findings of 66.3% among operated orthopaedic patients in Kenyatta National Hospital Nairobi in Kenya.^[29] However, in the Kenyan study, the mean age of patients was 35.39 years and the majority of the patients were 26 to 30 years. This differs from our finding of a mean age of 54.1 years, although the Kenyan study reported on blood transfusion in elective orthopaedic surgery while this study described both elective and emergency surgeries. Our study shares similarities with the age range of General Surgery patients from the same centre who received an intraoperative blood transfusion.^[30] Fifty-nine pints of blood were transfused to 43 orthopaedic patients (TI = 1.4) over a year period in this study, which is similar to the observation of 224 units transfused to 146 orthopaedic patients (TI = 1.5) in Dar-es-salaam.^[31] There is also some similarity with the 109 units of blood transfused to 82 patients (TI = 1.3) reported in a study on the rate of blood usage among orthopaedic patients in Zarqa, Jordan.^[32] While a study had questioned the routine use of blood transfusions in orthopaedic surgeries highlighting wastages,^[33] another author advocated Patient Blood Management Program in orthopaedic surgery involving meticulous surgical technique, optimal surgical blood-saving techniques, standardised transfusion triggers, and detection and treatment of pre-operative anaemia.^[34] ORIF for fractures constituted the highest single type of surgery carried out followed by below-knee amputation and hemiarthroplasty. Our finding differs from the observations in Canadian hospitals where knee arthroplasty, hip arthroplasty, and hip fracture surgery were the most commonly performed surgeries.^[28] Our finding is in agreement with previous observations in Sub-Saharan Africa where the greatest need for blood transfusion was following road traffic accidents (RTA), communal clashes, insurgency, and others (malaria, malnutrition, pregnancy-related complications, and a heavy burden of infectious diseases).^[35] Road traffic accidents (RTA), communal clashes, and insurgency may have accounted for the high prevalence of ORIF done among orthopaedic surgeries in this study. These occurrences have been reported in our region of practice.^[36-40] Blood transfusion indices in our study revealed a transfusion index (TI) of 1.37. This value is greater than 0.5, indicating significant blood utilization.^[26] Our value is lower than that observed in an Iranian study in the operating room in a general hospital where a value of 2.49 was reported.^[41] However, this value is higher than a TI of 0.7 reported for spine surgeries in a regional trauma center in Nigeria.^[42] One reason why the intraoperative blood transfusion burden is relatively high could be possibly due to preoperative anemia, which was not evaluated in this study. This study therefore opens an opportunity for further research on the preoperative anemia status among orthopedic patients in our environment. “Patients’ Blood Management Program” may be helpful among these patients.

Study Limitations: Data collected on the use of blood products was limited to usage intraoperatively.

We are unable to calculate the Crossmatch to Transfusion Ratio (C-TR), and the Transfusion Probability (TP) absence of data on a total number of units of blood cross-matched specific for orthopedic surgery.

Conclusion

A bimodal age distribution was observed in intraoperative blood transfusion requirement for patients between 41-60 years (trauma), and patients between 71-80 years (metabolic diseases). Of the observed orthopaedic intraoperative blood transfusion burden of 13.74% observed, open reduction and internal fixation for fractures was the highest single type of surgery carried out.

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